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Data Management Plan

Deliverable 8.1

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Physics of Microbial Motility

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Table 1 Abbreviations

CVS	Comma Separated Values
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EPS	Encapsulated Post Script
ESR	Early Stage Researcher
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Re-usable
MOV	Quick Time Video Format
MPC	Multi Particle Collision Dynamics
MPEG	Moving Pictures Experts Group
PDF	Portable Document Format
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PI	Principal Investigator
TB	Terabyte
TIF	Tag Image File Format
TXT	Text
VMD	Visual Molecular Dynamics
WP	Work Package

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0. About this deliverable

Due to the multi-disciplinary character of the PHYMOT consortium, where physicists, biologists, chemists, and engineers work together with different experimental, theoretical, and simulation approaches we are challenged to deal with a large variety of data types, in various formats and in file sizes. Naturally, data are collected or generated in some sort of raw data format, then processed (filtered, averaged, ...) after which the desired quantities can be extracted from the data to be finally presented in the form of graphs or tables. The main purpose of this deliverable is to provide guidelines for data documentation and data storage so as to comply with FAIR data management as required by the EU. This approach is beneficial also to the scientists at work as it provides structure, clarity, and guidance in handling data.

This document will be updated as the project progresses and in close collaboration with all beneficiaries. The input of all beneficiaries is essential for a successful implementation of a common strategy to handle the research data.

1. Data Summary

1.1 The purpose of data collection and generation

Within PHYMOT, data collection, generation, and analysis provide the primary information source for answering the research questions posed in the Workpackages WP1, WP2 and WP3 in the DoA.

1.2 Data types, formats and size

The projects in PHYMOT are diverse in nature and involve experimental studies as well as computer simulations and theoretical studies. Therefore the data formats are also diverse. In all cases, data will be collected either in an experimental set-up or by numerical or analytical calculations.

Simulations and other theoretical approaches typically involve input/output data [.txt, binary trajectory files, image formats PNG, PDF, movie formats .MPEG, .MOV, VMD

Experimental studies produce for instance images, movies, tracking data [.txt, image formats PNG, PDF, TIFF; movie formats .MOV, .MPEG

In all approaches, raw data might be processed (filtered, averaged, ...) to further determine the quantities of interest. This may affect file format and file size. Information on data origin, collection, and processing will be stored in metadata files of which a template is attached.

The description of data types, formats, and sizes may have to be adapted over time as the project progresses.

1.3 Data re-usage

Within the PHYMOT DoA, no re-use of existing data is explicitly foreseen but this does not exclude that data will be re-used for purpose of comparison.

1.4 Data origin and data size

Data collected and generated in PHYMOT stems from experimental studies (microscopy images, video microscopy movies,), numerical studies (MPC computer simulations), and other numerical and analytical calculations. These are all very data-intensive methodologies. Data production is, without giving a precise number, expected to be on the TB-scale where a substantial amount will originate from computer simulations and videomicroscopy.

1.5 Data usage outside PHYMOT

The data collected and generated within PHYMOT will be primarily useful for researchers in the field of active matter. Some advanced innovative technologies in data acquisition and data analysis might also be used in the much broader field of biophysics and soft matter.

2. FAIR data

Each PHYMOT beneficiary will have a local data manager appointed by the local PHYMOT principal investigator. Together, these data managers will form the PHYMOT data management workgroup. This group will identify

bottlenecks in the implementation in FAIR and generate ideas to implement solutions. The global PHYMOT data manager (Vliegthart, Jülich) will have a coordinating task in this group.

2.1 PHYMOT at Zenodo

The central strategy for implementing FAIR data management is that PHYMOT provides a community space called ITN-PHYMOT at Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>). Here PHYMOT scientists can upload (processed) data that has either been used for scientific publications beforehand, data that has not been published yet, or data sets that are potentially interesting for future studies.

Instructions for uploading data sets to Zenodo are provided on the PHYMOT website under internal.

2.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

To make data findable Zenodo requires the users to provide user and data information upon upload of data files. These data files will always be complemented with extensive metadata in a readme file in plain text (UTF-8) format. For this readme file, PHYMOT data management provides a template based on <https://cornell.app.box.com/v/ReadmeTemplate>. This template, which is attached as Appendix A, has some fixed elements but is yet flexible enough such that it can serve its purpose in all different research fields in PHYMOT. For all datasets uploaded in Zenodo, a DOI will be available automatically. Moreover, Zenodo provides an interface for entering the most important information as metadata. A selection of keywords provided from a list from the PHYMOT website is entered upon uploading the data. These metadata are searchable by the Zenodo search engine.

2.1.2 Filename conventions and versioning

File names will be uniquely assigned and have the following structure

PHY_YYY_vz.zip

where YYY is a descriptive part of the filename, vz the data version (z=1,2,3..), and .zip the extension of the compressed and zipped package. This package contains also the metadata file with the name PHY_YYY_meta_vz.txt

2.1.3 Optimizing data re-use

To increase the options for data re-use, each PHYMOT will provide a minimum of 4 keywords when uploading a data set to Zenodo. A list of keywords that is regularly updated will be published on the PHYMOT website. A draft version of this list is attached as Appendix B to this document.

2.1.4 Detailed metadata for data sets

For biophysics in general there is no metadata standard yet. We, therefore, have chosen to use a template from <https://cornell.app.box.com/v/ReadmeTemplate> to include extra metadata, apart from the metadata entered upon submission at Zenodo. This additional file will contain extra information on samples, sample processing, methodology, file structure.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Open data in PHYMOT

PHYMOTs local project supervisors are primarily responsible for decisions on when to publish which data on Zenodo. This may depend on manuscript status, patent application, commercial sensitivity as laid out in the Consortium Agreement. PHYMOTs project management encourages all beneficiaries to publish all (processed) data that belongs to manuscripts accepted for publication. Due to file size restrictions publication of raw data will not be promoted in general. However, all raw data linked to published data will be available upon request to the owners. The metadata file will contain the contact information of the owner(s) of the raw data.

2.2.2 Accessing PHYMOT data

PHYMOTs data will be uploaded to the PHYMOT Zenodo community space. Data will be stored in such a way that data can be accessed without commercial software. Metadata, documentation, and if applicable code and scripts will be stored with the data. Data published at Zenodo will be openly accessible by all registered Zenodo users. For raw data generated by commercial instruments, we cannot guarantee in advance that they can be read without the software from the instrument manufacturer.

2.3. Making data interoperable

PHYMOTs beneficiaries have their roots in the biophysical community where PHYMOT there no special data standards or ontologies (as in crystallography or astrophysics). However, the data will be stored and documented

such that it can be easily re-used. PHYMOT will store numerical data preferably as comma-separated variables (CSV) that can be read by any text editor. If more specialized software is required this will be indicated in the metadata file.

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

Zenodo provides the 4 standard options for data re-usage under Creative Commons Attribution International 4.0

1) Open: This license **lets others distribute, remix, tweak, and build upon our work, even commercially**, as long as they give credit for the original creation. This is the most accommodating of licenses offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.

2) Embargo: Required only for Embargoed Access uploads. Format: YYYY-MM-DD. The date your upload will be made publicly available in case it is under an embargo period from your publisher.

3) Restricted: Specify the conditions under which you grant users access to the files in your upload. The user requesting access will be asked to justify how they fulfill the conditions. Based on the justification, you decide whom to grant/deny access. You are not allowed to charge users for granting access to data hosted on Zenodo.

4) Closed:

Data corresponding to scientific publications will be made available after publication in a peer-reviewed journal. At that moment also the raw data will be available for re-use.

3. Allocation of resources

Personnel costs of the local data managers (Gerrit Vliegthart, JUL +) are covered by the central (local) PHYMOT budget

4. Data security

Raw data is locally stored and data security will be locally provided. Processed data will be stored at Zenodo. Zenodo guarantees safe data storage for 20 years which fulfills EU regulations.

5. Ethical aspects

PHYMOT only deals with non-personal data which is not of any ethical concern.

6. Other issues

Local regulations for beneficiaries concerning data management are outlined in references 1-11 below

References

- 1) Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany
https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/principles_dfg_funding/research_data/index.html
- 2) Danmarks Tekniske Universitet, Denmark
<https://www.dtu.dk/english/research/research-framework/research-data-management>
- 3) University of Cambridge, United Kingdom
<https://www.data.cam.ac.uk>
- 4) Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule, Switzerland
<https://ethz.ch/services/en/service/a-to-z/research-data.html>
- 5) Universität Würzburg, Germany

<https://www.uni-wuerzburg.de/rdm/startseite/>

6) Universität Basel, Switzerland

<https://researchdata.unibas.ch/en/>

7) Universitat de les Illes Balears, Spain

<https://digital.csic.es/bitstream/10261/173801/2/Maredata-recommendations-ENG.pdf>

8) École Supérieure de Physique et de Chimie Industrielles de la ville de Paris, France

https://www.science-ouverte.cnrs.fr/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Cnrs_Research-Data-Plan_mars21.pdf

9) Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France

???

10) Università Degli Studi Di Roma La Sapienza, Italy

???

Appendix A: Metadata template

Metadata template version v1

Date: Sept. 18 2021

Author Gerrit Vliegthart, Forschungszentrum Jülich

Status: Draft

The metadata template below is to be filled out and uploaded with datasets uploaded to the PHYMOT community space at Zenodo. It is based on the template provided at <https://cornell.app.box.com/v/ReadmeTemplate>. This template will be available at https://etn-phymot.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/metadata_template_v1.txt

GENERAL INFORMATION

1. Title of Dataset:

2. Author Information

A. Principal Investigator Contact Information

Name:
Institution:
Address:
Email:
Orcid:

3. Date of data collection (single date, range, approximate date)
<YYYY-MM-DD>:

4. Geographic location of data collection <city/region, State, Country, as appropriate>:

5. Information about funding sources that supported the collection of the data:

A. Grant agency: EU

B. Grant number:

C. Project title: PHYMOT
i. Workpackage:
ii. Deliverable:

D. Beneficiary:

(choose JUL, UIB, URS, UWU, UNIBAS, ETH, BGU, ECB, ESPCI, LYN, SYN, UCAM)

6. Relation with other beneficiaries or partners in PHYMOT (for instance in a mini-project or secondment)

A. Principal Investigator Contact Information

Name:
Institution:
Address:

Email:
Orcid:

7. Keywords (method, species, phenomenology)

SHARING/ACCESS INFORMATION

1. Licenses/restrictions placed on the data:
2. Links to publications that cite or use the data:
 - A. Journal, title, volume pages (year)
 - B. doi
3. Links to other publicly accessible locations of the data:
4. Links/relationships to ancillary data sets:
5. Was data derived from another source? yes/no
 - A. If yes, list source(s):
6. Recommended citation for this dataset:

DATA & FILE OVERVIEW

1. File List:
<list all files (or folders, as appropriate for dataset organization) contained in the dataset, with a brief description>
2. Relationship between files, if important:
3. Additional related data collected that was not included in the current data package:
4. Are there multiple versions of the dataset? yes/no
 - A. If yes, name of file(s) that was updated:
 - i. Why was the file updated?
 - ii. When was the file updated?
 - iii. What is the modification?

INFORMATION ON SAMPLE (complete the list to your liking)

1. Species of microorganism and origin
2. Concentration
3. Medium composition
4. Nutrient composition and concentration
5. Other relevant parameters
6.
7.

METHODOLOGICAL INFORMATION

1. Description of methods used for collection/generation of data: (microscopy, simulation, ...)

<Include links or references to publications or other documentation containing experimental design or protocols used in data collection>

2. Methods for processing the data: (averaging, filtering,)
<describe how the submitted data were generated from the raw or collected data>

3. Instrument- or software-specific information needed to interpret the data:
<include full name and version of software, and any necessary packages or libraries needed to run scripts>

4. Standards and calibration information, if appropriate:

5. Environmental/experimental conditions:

6. Describe any quality-assurance procedures performed on the data:

7. People involved with sample collection, processing, analysis and/or submission:

DATA-SPECIFIC INFORMATION FOR: [FILENAME]

<repeat this section for each dataset, folder or file, as appropriate>

1. Number of variables:

2. Number of cases/rows:

3. Variable List:

<list variable name(s), description(s), unit(s) and value labels as appropriate for each>

4. Missing data codes:

<list code/symbol and definition>n

5. Specialized formats or other abbreviations used:

Appendix B: List of Keywords

A Selection of Keywords in this list is to be used as entry in the Zenodo database when uploading a dataset. These keywords are important for your dataset to be found and to be re-used. Use at least three keywords from each section (if you can). The list is under constant revision. Please send (suggestions of other) keywords to etn-phymot@fz-juelich.de.

Methodology

3D-tracking
3D holography
3D-correlative light-electron microscopy
3D-Lagrangian tracking
Active rheology
Atomic force microscopy
Brownian Dynamics
Digital holographic microscopy
Direct numerical simulations
Genetic modification
Holographic microscopy
Imaging Microscopy
Mesoscale simulations
Microfluidics
Microrheology
Multi-DDM analysis
Multi Particle Collision Dynamics
Optical trapping
Robotic stirring
Simulations
Video analysis
Video microscopy

Systems

Algae
Bacteria
Bacillus subtilis
Chlamydomonas reinhardtii
Cilia
Cyanobacteria Trichodesmium
E. coli
Epithelial tissues
Eukaryotes
Flagella
Flagellar axoneme
Magnetotactic bacteria
Marine parasites
Nanoflagellates
Parasites
Peritrichous bacteria
Planktonic bacteria
Self-propelled particles
Trypanobots
Trypanosomes

Phenomenology

Bacterial locomotion
Bacterial swarming
Beat pattern
Cell-cell scattering
Cell feeding
Cell motility-dynamics
Chemosensing
Chemotaxis
Cilia synchronisation
Collective motion
Flagellar mechanics
Mechanosensing
Quorum sensing
Run-and-tumble
Run-reverse-flick

